

MODELLING OF CURING STRESSES IN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, four models were combined to describe the development history of curing stresses. The contribution of chemical shrinkage to curing stress development and the residual stress relaxation characterized by glass transition region were considered. The four models are: 1) A model describing the temperature field. 2) A model describing the change of mechanical and physical parameters. 3) A model describing the micro-curing stress in the longitudinal direction of UDC. 4) A model describing the lamination curing stresses in symmetric cross-ply laminate.

INTRODUCTION

During the curing of epoxy-based composites, because of the chemical shrinkage and thermal expansion of the matrix which are higher than the fiber, the transverse direction of a lamina has larger potential of deformation than the longitudinal direction. Depending upon the problem to be solved and its starting point to solve the problem, residual stresses of different origins corresponding to material structures of different levels will appear in the composite material during its curing process. The curing process of composite materials is an irreversible dynamical process. The properties of composite materials depend on the curing schedule selected. Therefore, composite materials can be considered as the result of the process, they have a memory of the process.

To study and take advantages of the influence of the curing process on the properties of the composite materials, it is helpful to search the rule under the changes occurred in the curing system during the whole curing process. Complicated as the curing process is, there must be some fundamental relations governing the process, which are similar to other macro-process.

Modelling approach is necessary to describe the dynamical process. In this paper, the modelling is stressed on the residual stresses in the material of uniform microscopic structure during its fabrication. With the application of classical lamination theory and micromechanics, only the general tendency of internal stresses is predicted.

MODELLING OF THE RESIDUAL STRESS HISTORY

1. Modelling of the temperature field.

The temperatures in the laminate have to be known to calculate the residual stresses because many parameters involved depend on it. Because of the coupling of temperature-deformation-curing reaction¹, the temperature field can't be solely determined in the strict sense. Fourier equation holds only if the volume of the space unit keeps constant and is used as an approximate equation to treat the heat transfer problem.

For simplicity, the coupling effects are neglected. Heat transfer is assumed in the direction normal to the laminate in conduction manner. The heat transfer process can be approximately described by the following equation²:

$$\rho c \frac{\delta T}{\delta t} = K \frac{\delta^2 T}{\delta Z^2} + \rho \dot{H} \quad [1]$$

where ρ, c are the density and specific heat of the laminate, K is the thermal conduction coef-

ficient of the laminate in the normal direction. \dot{H} is the rate of heat generation of the curing reaction in the laminate.

$$\dot{H} = d\alpha / dt \cdot H_R = f(T, \alpha) H_R \quad [2]$$

$$\alpha = H / H_R \quad [3]$$

where α is the cure degree of the matrix, H_R is the total heat generated during the complete cure of the composite laminate, $d\alpha / dt = f(T, \alpha)$ is the kinetic equation of the cure reaction. \dot{H} , H_R and $d\alpha / dt$ are related to the type of the matrix and the fiber content and the coupling agent used. The initial and boundary conditions for eq. [1] are referred to 2.

With the combination of the curing kinetic equation, the solution of the above equation yields the distribution of temperature, degree of cure, rate of temperature change and rate of curing reaction. Because α can't describe the structure features of the matrix completely, the parameters of the matrix or laminate can't be obtained only on the basis of α .

2. Modelling of physical and mechanical parameters during curing process

The irreversible thermodynamic fluctuation theory can be applied to describe the change of physical and mechanical parameters of the curing system directly³. Application of the theory assumes that only one reaction dominates the situation in any system to which it is applied⁴. The cure reaction can be treated as multiple chemical reactions in which each chemical reaction is related to a thermodynamic ordering parameter ζ_i . The variation of physical or mechanical properties of the system during curing can be modelled as the time correlation function of the mean square fluctuation of ordering parameters. Because of the similarity between the kinetic process of cure and the molecular structural relaxation process, the physical or mechanical properties of polymer system during cure may be expressed as:

$$[P_\infty - P(t)] / [P_\infty - P_0] = \sum W_i \langle (\Delta \zeta_i)^2 \rangle \exp[-(t / \tau_i)] \quad [4]$$

where P_0 and P_∞ are the initial and final physical or mechanical properties during the cure of the matrix, $P(t)$ is the property at time t , $\langle (\Delta \zeta_i)^2 \rangle$ is the mean square fluctuation of the ordering parameter ζ_i for the reaction. The latter may be expressed as:⁴

$$\langle (\Delta \zeta_i)^2 \rangle = kT / (\delta^2 G / \delta \zeta_i^2)_{P,T,X} = -kT / (\delta A / \delta \zeta_i)_{P,T,X} \quad [5]$$

where k is Boltzmann's constant and A the affinity, P , T , X , are pressure, absolute temperature and total mole fraction. In eq. [4], W_i is the weight constant and τ_i is the relaxation time of the chemical reaction associated with ordering parameter ζ_i . This is generalized from a sum of single relaxation processes to a continuous distribution of such processes. The distribution function relaxation spectrum for the analog of eq. [4] is:

$$[P_\infty - P(t)] / [P_\infty - P_0] = \exp[-(t / \tau)^\beta] \quad [6]$$

where β is the constant describing the width of the relaxation spectrum.

$$\tau = \tau_0 \exp(\Delta H / RT) \quad [7]$$

where τ_0 is a constant, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute cure temperature and ΔH is the activation energy of the cure reaction.

In eq. [6], P_0 and P_∞ can be measured or assumed. After the values of τ_0 , ΔH and β at the curing condition are determined, $P(t)$ can be evaluated by

$$P(t) = P_\infty - (P_\infty - P_0) \exp\{-[t / \tau_0 \exp(-\Delta H / RT(t))]^\beta\} \quad [8]$$

$\langle (\Delta \zeta)^2 \rangle$ is also associated with changes of volume and compressibility of the curing system.

3. Modelling of residual stress in the longitudinal direction of U.D.C. at microscopic level

The temperature and time corresponding to the completion of resin flow are taken as T and $t=0$ respectively. The matrix is assumed to be homogeneous and isotropic. No slide at the fiber-matrix interface takes place. The material has uniform microscopic structure.

The longitudinal residual stresses in the fiber and the matrix due to the curing of matrix and the temperature change are denoted as σ_{fL} and σ_{rL} . The fiber volume ratio is V_f . The resin volume ratio is $V = 1 - V_f$. The volume ratio is supposed to be insensitive to temperature change and curing reaction with no external force acting on the material. The force equilibrium and geometry compatibility equations may be expressed as⁵:

$$V_f d\sigma_{fL} + V_r d\sigma_{rL} = 0 \quad [9]$$

$$d\epsilon_{fL} = d\epsilon_{rL} \quad [10]$$

For a specified curing schedule, the temperature is related to time:

$$T = T(t) \quad [11]$$

$$d\epsilon_{fL} = d\sigma_{fL} / E_f + \alpha_f T'(t) dt \quad [12]$$

$$d\epsilon_{rL} = d\sigma_{rL} / E_r(T,t) + \alpha_r T'(t) dt + \alpha_t dt \quad [13]$$

where α_f and α_r are the thermal expansion coefficients for the fiber and matrix respectively and α_t is the shrinkage coefficient related to the matrix and the cure schedule adopted. Combination of the above equations gives the derivative of the residual stress in the matrix:

$$d\sigma_{rL} = E_f E_r(T,t) V_f [(\alpha_f - \alpha_r) T'(t) - \alpha_t] dt / [E_f V_f + E_r(T,t) V_r] \quad [14]$$

The derivative of the residual stress in the fiber is:

$$d\sigma_{fL} = E_f E_r(T,t) V_r [(\alpha_r - \alpha_f) T'(t) + \alpha_t] dt / [E_f V_f + E_r(T,t) V_r] \quad [15]$$

During the curing process, the residual stress in the matrix developed from the onset of gelation and the termination of resin flow ($t=0$) to a time t is:

$$\sigma_{rL} = \int_0^t E_f E_r(T,t) V_f [(\alpha_f - \alpha_r) T'(t) - \alpha_t] dt / [E_f V_f + E_r(T,t) V_r] \quad [16]$$

The residual stress in the fiber at the same time t is:

$$\sigma_{fL} = \int_0^t E_f E_r(T,t) V_r [(\alpha_r - \alpha_f) T'(t) + \alpha_t] dt / [E_f V_f + E_r(T,t) V_r] \quad [17]$$

If t is taken as the onset time of the glass transition of the matrix in the longitudinal direction due to curing t_g , $\sigma_{rL}^{t_g}$ and $\sigma_{fL}^{t_g}$ are the residual stress at time t_g , the relation between them follows eq.[9].

The relaxation time in the glass transition region of the matrix is denoted as τ . Assume that stress relaxation is dominant in this region and Maxwell model can be applied to describe the relaxation process. The dependence of relaxation upon temperature is approximatized here. The internal stress in the matrix in the 0° direction at time t is:

$$\sigma_{rL}' = \sigma_{rL}^{t_g} \exp[-(t - t_g) / \tau] \exp[-\Delta H / RT(t)] \quad [18]$$

where ΔH is the activation energy of the stress relaxation process, R is the gas constant, $T(t)$ is the temperature path. Although the fiber can be considered to be linear elastic, the internal stress in the fiber is governed by eq.[9]. it decays in the same way.

The time at the termination of glass transition of the matrix in the longitudinal direction and the entrance to glass state is taken as t_e . t_e is brought into eq.[18] to obtain $\sigma_{rL}^{t_e}$ which is then brought into eq.[9] to obtain $\sigma_{fL}^{t_e}$. They are the residual stresses at the termination of glass transition. The relaxation of the residual stresses are no longer considered as the matrix in longitudinal direction is in glass state. Both chemical shrinkage and cooling of the composite will increase the internal stress in the material.

If the time for the complete cure of the matrix is taken as t_c , $\alpha t = 0$ when $t > t_c$. With this in mind, the changes of residual stresses at time t can also be obtained from eq. [16] and [17].

The rate of residual stress change in the matrix is

$$d\sigma_{RL} / dt = E_j E_R(T, t) V_j [(\alpha_j - \alpha_R) T'(t) - \alpha t] / [E_j V_j + E_R(T, t) V_R] \quad [19]$$

if the matrix is completely cured and the cooling rate of the laminate is slow, the residual stresses will be insensitive to the temperature path for cooling.

If the physical or chemical stress relaxation due to the imperfection in the matrix structure and the wave like buckling of the fiber in the matrix exist. The values of the residual stress will be decreased.

4. Lamination residual stresses in the on-axis direction of the lamina in the symmetric cross-ply laminate during cure.

The thermochemical in-plane internal stress resultant is:

$$N_i = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} Q_{ij} \epsilon_j^{s,r} dz \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad [20]$$

where h is the thickness of the laminate, z is the coordinate in the thickness direction, ϵ_j is the strain produced by chemical shrinkage and temperature change. Q_{ij} is the reduced stiffness component corresponding to $\epsilon_j^{s,r}$, it is related to temperature and the cure degree of the matrix.

$$d\epsilon_j^{s,r} = \alpha_j(t) dt \quad [21]$$

where $\alpha_j(t)$ is the rate of free dimensional change of the lamina, it is related to the cure schedule.

$$N_i^r = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} dz \int_0^t Q_{ij}(t) \alpha_j(t) dt \quad [22]$$

where $t=0$ is at the stress-free state corresponding to the termination of resin flow.

The thermal strains of the laminate is evaluated by classical lamination theory:

$$\epsilon_j^{o,r} = A_j^{-1} N_i^r \quad [23]$$

The residual stress components are:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma &= Q_{ij}(t) (\epsilon_j^{o,r} - \epsilon_j^{s,r}) \\ &= Q_{ij}(t) A_j^{-1} K N K - Q_{ij}(t) - \int_0^t \alpha_j(t) dt \\ &= Q_{ij}(t) A_j^{-1} K \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} dz \int_0^t Q_{ij}(t) \alpha_j(t) dt - Q_{ij}(t) \int_0^t \alpha_j(t) dt \end{aligned} \quad [24]$$

It is assumed that the residual stresses are relaxed to zero in the glass transition region. The residual stresses accumulated only when the temperature of the laminate is under T_g . The internal stresses can be calculated by eq. [24]. The lamination residual stresses are completely caused by temperature change.

The thermal lamination residual stresses in the laminate at the end of fabrication are: ⁵⁻⁶

$$\begin{aligned} [\sigma_i] &= [Q_{ij} A_j^{-1} K N K - Q_{ij} \epsilon_j^r] \\ &= [Q_{ij} A_j^{-1} K \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} Q_{ij} dz \int_{T_x}^T \alpha_j(T) dT - Q_{ij} \int_{T_x}^T \alpha_j(T) dT] \end{aligned} \quad [25]$$

The dimensional change of the laminate is:

$$[\epsilon_j^{\sigma, \tau}] = [A_j^{-1}] [N_i^T] = [Q_j] [N_i^T]$$

In UDC, only microresidual stress exists. For the laminate discussed above, lamination residual stresses exist at the lamina level. At the microscopic level of angle-ply laminate, the field of the residual stresses are the summation of the lamination residual stresses and the microresidual stress, whether the summation is necessary depends on the problem to be solved.

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